

Elijan themes in the *Liber de institutione primorum monachorum*

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1 Introduction

The *Liber de institutione primorum monachorum... ad Caprasium monachum* has some claim to be considered not only the classic expression of the Elijah traditions of the Carmelite order but also the most significant work of medieval Carmelite spirituality after the Rule of Saint Albert.¹ Attributed to John, forty-fourth bishop of Jerusalem (who occupied the see from 387-417),² in its present form it is the work of Felip Ribot (†1391), Carmelite provincial of Catalonia.³ The *Institutio* forms the first seven books of a larger collection of works compiled by Ribot entitled *Decem libri de institutione et peculiaribus gestis religiosorum carmelitarum*.

The other works in the collection are:

2) The letter of Cyril (8:1-3; 7:6), which relates the writing of the *Institutio*, the reorganisation of the order by Aymeric of Malafaïda in 1141, the work of Berthold and Brocard, the prohibition of the white cloak by the Saracens, etc. Most notably, this work gives the original Albertine text of the Rule (8:3), which has sometimes been considered a reconstruction but which almost certainly was based on either the original text or some detailed information about it.⁴

3) A treatise on the Rule (8:5-7) attributed to Sibert de Beka (provincial of Germany 1317-32), largely a defence of the legitimacy of the Rule and its approval under various popes, as well as an important account of the circumstances of its revision under Innocent IV.

¹ The best edition currently available is that of Daniel of the Virgin Mary in the *Speculum Carmelitanum* of 1680, 1:1-71. A new critical edition is in preparation.

² The best modern treatment of John is by Daniel Stiernon, 'Jean de Jérusalem', in *Dictionnaire de Spiritualité* 8 (1974): 565-574, with bibliography. In the standard modern reckoning, John is counted the forty-third bishop of Jerusalem: P.B. Gams, *Series Episcoporum Ecclesiae Catholicae*, Regensburg 1873, repr. Leipzig 1931, 459.

³ Comparatively little is known of his life. Basic details can be found in Cosmé de Saint Etienne de Villiers, *Bibliotheca Carmelitana, notis criticis et dissertationibus illustrata*, Orléans, 1752; reprint ed. G. Wessels, Romae: in aedibus Collegii S. Alberti, 1927, 2:639-641; Bartholomaeus M. Xiberta, *De scriptoribus scholasticis saeculi XIV ex ordine Carmelitarum*, (Bibliothèque de la Revue d'Histoire Ecclésiastique, fasc. 6), Louvain: Bureaux de la Revue, 1931), 45-46; Jaume de Puig i Oliver, 'El Tractatus de haeresi et de infidelium incredulitate et de horum criminum iudice, de Felip Ribot, O.Carm.', in *Arxiu de Textos Catalans Antics*, 1 (1982) 127-190; and especially Balbino Velasco Bayón, *Historia del Carmelo Español*, Vol. 1: *Desde los orígenes hasta finalizar el Concilio de Trento c. 1265-1563*, Rome 1990, 216-219.

⁴ I hope to publish an edition of this text in the near future.

4) The Chronicle of William of Sandwich (9:1–8), which recounts the early spread of the order in Europe, the destruction of the province of the Holy Land, and the last days on Mount Carmel in 1291. William was defensor of the Holy Land province at the general chapter of 1287, and although the chronicle is generally considered spurious, I think it very likely that at least some part of it is an authentic witness to the events it relates.

5) An account of the privileges of the order and various papal bulls in its favour (10:1–8), compiled by Ribot.

Ribot claims to be only the redactor or editor of works by older Carmelite authors, with the exception of his collection of bulls in Book 10 and some interpolations here and there, for which he clearly indicates his authorship. The truth of this claim and the authenticity of the works involved has been the subject of dispute since the mid-seventeenth century and even earlier. Although modern scholars have been inclined to attribute the whole of the *Decem libri* to Ribot himself,⁵ more recently the conviction has been growing that the collection does indeed contain older material, as suggested above, although in the present state of research it is not yet possible to come to any firm conclusions from a redaction-critical point of view, and a large number of textual and hermeneutical problems still remain to be resolved.

The Ribot collection is a complex document. Although the works it contains are attributed to various authors and times from the fifth century to the fourteenth and are diverse in genre, style and content, they have been edited to form a more or less continuous ‘history’ of the Order from the time of its alleged foundation by the prophet Elijah until Ribot’s own time. And more than a history alone, the work provides a portrait of the order and its characteristic spirituality as it had developed at the end of the fourteenth century. Drawing on the Carmelite literature of the previous century and a half—which Fr Staring has succinctly characterised as ‘reflections on the nature of the order’—Ribot’s work achieved a harmonious synthesis of sometimes disparate material.⁶ The *Institutio*, especially, came to have an enormous, if sometimes indirect, influence on the Order and its spirituality. The literary and artistic skill with which apparently diverse elements have been brought together, and the harmony of theological and spiritual outlook which seems to underlie the various parts of the collection, suggests that for the purpose of interpretation it should be viewed as a whole, an approach which has so far been entirely lacking. A better understanding than we have at present of the structure of the whole collection may provide hermeneutical clues for the interpretation of its parts and perhaps also additional evidence for the identification of the various redactional levels which it contains.

What is true of the Ribot collection as a whole is also true of its most substantial, complex and influential part, the *Liber de institutione*, to the structure of which we should now turn our attention.

⁵ Smet summarises: ‘... lately the considered judgement of students is that these works do not antedate their publication by Ribot’; *Carmelites*, 1:54.

⁶ For a summary treatment of this literature see E. Boaga, ‘La storiografia carmelitana nei secoli XIII e XIV’, in Paul Chandler and Keith J. Egan, eds, *The Land of Carmel: Essays in Honour of Joachim Smet*, Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1991, 125–154.

2 The structure of the *Liber de institutione*

In the modern history of the *Institutio* Gabriel Wessels is both hero and villain. His publication of an extract of the text in the *Analecta Ordinis Carmelitarum* in 1916 was apparently the first publication since 1684.⁷ Wessels drew a new degree of attention to this important Carmelite work, and may be said to have touched off modern study of it. Almost every writer on the *Institutio* quotes or misquotes his statement that before the seventeenth century the first part of the *Institutio* was the principal spiritual reading of Carmelites⁸—although in fact the paucity of small economic manual editions of the work may well indicate that it was, as it is today, more revered than read, and that its undoubted influence was largely indirect.

Unfortunately, in choosing to publish an extract of the *Institutio* (consisting of Book 1 chapters 2–8 and Book 2 chapter 1) and dubbing it the *pars ascetica* of the work, Wessels did much to obscure its real structure and to discourage attention to its remaining forty-eight chapters, which have rarely been translated and seldom studied. The *pars ascetica* is Wessels' own construct, made up of from chapters 2–8 of book 1 and chapter 1 of book 2. The title *pars ascetica*, nowhere justified by the text, reflects the unease of his time with the language of mysticism and its somewhat rigid distinction of 'ascetical' and 'mystical' aspects of spiritual life.⁹ He thus obscured the spiritual character of the work, which, following the traditional monastic teaching of John Cassian and others, presents ascetical effort and mystical experience as a single spiritual dynamic centred in transforming love: the *Institutio* presents Carmelite spirituality as both an asceticism and a mysticism of love in which the false dichotomies of action and contemplation, ascesis and mysticism, find no place. However, Wessels' construct has continued to be influential, has been the basis of numerous modern translations, and is probably the guise in which most contemporary Carmelites have encountered this text.¹⁰

The structural principle of the *Institutio* is not a division into 'ascetical' and 'historical' parts, but is rather to be found in medieval biblical hermeneutic. Throughout most of the patristic and medieval periods, the principal exegetical tool was the doctrine of the four senses of scripture: the first and foundation of the others was the literal or historical sense, while the other three possible levels of meaning were spiritual or mystical senses:

⁷ 'Pars ascetica Regulae Ioannis 44', in *Anal.O.Carm.* 3 (1914–16): 346–367. This was not a new edition: Wessels reproduced the text published by Peter Wasteels in 1643 with the chapter headings of Thomas of Jesus' edition of 1599.

⁸ 'Regula Iohannis 44... quoad partem asceticam certe influxum in Ordinem exercuit. Ante saeculum XVII fuit praecipuus liber O[r]dinis n[ostri] pro lectione spirituali fratrum, praesertim postquam 1507 impressus erat'; 'Pars ascetica', 346.

⁹ Earlier, the Golden Letter of William of St Thierry had undergone a similar change in its reception: no longer regarded as 'a small *summa* of mystical theology, it had become merely a manual of asceticism, a "directory" which was admired for its wisdom and discretion...'; J.M. Déchanet, Introduction to *The Golden Epistle: A Letter to the Brethren at Mont Dieu*, trans. Theodore Berkeley, (Cistercian Fathers Series, 12), Kalamazoo Mi., 1980, x; see also xvii–xix.

¹⁰ Unfortunately there is as yet no complete translation of the *Institutio* into any modern language. The most complete are the English version by Norman Werling in *Sword* 4 (1940): 20–24 and following, and the Spanish version published anonymously by Valentino de San José (Avila 1959). Both, however, are based on defective Latin texts giving only 41 and 48 of the original 56 chapters. An English translation is in preparation.

the allegorical or Christological; the tropological or moral; and the anagogical or eschatological. The latter three were often considered collectively as the mystical sense, and in the later Middle Ages, and particularly in the preaching of the friars, the moral sense assumed a central place.¹¹

2.1 The mystical sense: the spiritual journey of Elijah

The starting point of the *Institutio* is a biblical text, 1 Kings 17:2-4, God's command to Elijah: 'Depart from here, go towards the east, and hide in the brook Carith, which is over against the Jordan. There you shall drink of the torrent, and I have commanded the ravens to feed you there'.

This text is first interpreted in its spiritual or mystical sense, according to which Elijah is called not only to a geographical journey but to an inner one, a journey of transformation in love. The first book of the *Institutio* traces this journey step by step, revealing paradoxically along the way that the exemplary life of Elijah in Carith is a response to a gospel call and a participation in the paschal mystery of the death and resurrection of Christ.

God's command draws Elijah into a series of renunciations or purifications, which demand a progressive conversion from sin to love and rediscovery of the original image of God within him. He must first purify his relationship to things, renouncing the possessions which encumber the heart, in order to find the freedom to hear the word of God ('Depart from here'). Second, he must purify his will, finding in the obedience of Christ the way of perfect conformity to God's will, which moves the attention of the heart to God and his future ('go eastward'). Third, he must purify his relationships with others, moving from the injustice symbolised by the city (Ps 54:10-12) to the state of attentiveness to God, readiness for grace and undividedness of heart which are the innermost meaning of solitude, silence and celibacy ('hide in the brook Carith'). The fourth step of this journey is a phase of integration, in which it becomes clear that the process of purification of the heart is in fact a process of growth in love, in which the soul is being conformed again to the original image of the God who is Love. Love is the fulfilling of the law, and the life to which Elijah is called is nothing other than a total surrender of self to God in love ('over against the Jordan'). The person who arrives at pure love is enabled to 'drink from the torrent', that is to experience perfect union with God and to be transformed in his love. However, in this life we are always on the journey; the 'perfection' of the *Institutio* is a dynamic rather than a static concept. God is ever before us, never seen but only glimpsed, always the transcendent One: life must be lived then in constant repentance, unceasing prayer, and in longing for the things that are ahead ('the ravens will feed you there').

Elijah had been considered the biblical type of monastic life since the very beginnings of monasticism in the fourth century: he was considered the first monk, through whom God wished to establish the monastic way of life. His journey, as a result, is the example or pattern of life for those who come after him. Therefore in the spiritual or mystical meaning of this text the religious reads not only God's call to Elijah but God's call to him-

¹¹ The standard work is Henri de Lubac, *Exégèse médiévale: Les quatre sens de l'Écriture*, 4 vols, Paris 1950-60.

self as well: here is revealed the whole inner dynamic of the religious vocation and of spiritual maturation.

2.2 The literal sense: the historical journey of the Order

The first book of the *Institutio*, or Wessel's *pars ascetica*, is more or less familiar to most Carmelites, at least as it has been filtered through Brenninger's spiritual directory and other works.¹² The remaining books, however, have been much neglected, no doubt because their account of the 'history' of the order's foundation by Elijah, its continuation by Elisha and the sons of the prophets into the time of John the Baptist and of the Messiah, and the conversion of the sons of the prophets to Christianity at Pentecost, has been seen merely as entirely outmoded legendary material. Indeed, it is astonishing to realise until how recently Carmelites maintained the medieval claims to an historical foundation from Elijah and an uninterrupted succession from him, claims that were not wholly abandoned until well into the present century. Now that no one entertains the legendary history of the order, and with the new receptivity to mythical and symbolic modes of expression which has been encouraged by modern hermeneutical approaches, it is possible to take up also the remaining parts of the *Institutio* from a fresh perspective.

After elaborating the mystical meaning of the programmatic text 1 Kings 17:2–4 in Book 1, the *Institutio* turns to the literal meaning of the same text. The journey which Elijah made at God's command was both a spiritual and a geographical one: his inner journey constituted him the exemplar and model of monastic life, while his geographical journey made him its *princeps*, its first practitioner, its father and founder. Thus a consideration of the literal sense of the text begins for us the history of the Order which would grow up around him. In this, the *Institutio* is in continuity with the earliest Palestinian kernel of the Carmelite tradition about Elijah, as evidenced in our oldest Carmelite text, the *Rubrica prima*, which stressed that he was both the model of Carmelite life and its historical founder.¹³ This is the subject of Books 2–5, which trace the development of the order in Carith and on Mount Carmel and the eventual conversion of the hermits to Christianity after the resurrection of Christ. (The sixth book deals with the relationship of Mary and Elijah, and the seventh with the symbolic significance of the habit).

The literal or historical sense of Scripture, of course, also has 'spiritual' content, and in fact in the historical books of the *Institutio* Elijah does not cease to be an exemplary figure. There is no doubt that medieval and early modern Carmelites read these parts of the work as literal histories, and the energies of generations of Carmelite scholars were spent in defence of these fictions, but they are better characterised as myth than as legend: in these stories Carmelites sought not only to connect themselves with Elijah through an uninterrupted historical succession, but also to express the inner meaning of their lives by giving it a concrete narrative form projected back into the past.

¹² [Joannes Brenninger, O.Carm.], *Directorium Carmelitanum vitae spiritualis, praesertim novitiis instruendis compilatum et prelo expressum iussu et auctoritate Reverendissimi Patris Hilarii Mariae Doswald, Prioris Generalis Carmelitarum*, In Civitate Vaticana: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1940; the English translation is *Carmelite Directory of the Spiritual Life*, trans. Leo J. Walter, Chicago, Ill.: Carmelite Press, 1951).

¹³ Cf. L. Saggi, 'Agiografia carmelitana', in *Santi del Carmelo*, Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1972, esp. 25–28; an English trans. by Paul Chandler, 'The Prophet Elijah and Carmelite Hagiography' (2021) is at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4882763>.

However, the 'history' of the Order presented in these books does not represent a static self-understanding but a dynamic one. In its literal sense, as in its mystical one, 1 Kings 17:2–4 is also concerned with a journey. Elijah's journey to Carith is also the starting point of the historical journey of the Order, and like his inner journey this is also a story of transformation: the sons of the prophets founded by Elijah will find the fullness of their vocation in the coming of the Messiah, in their spiritual affinity with the Virgin Mary, their conversion by the apostles, and their life and mission in the Christian community. In a sort of inclusion, the text of 1 Kings which stands at the head of this history gives way at the end to Acts 2:42–47, the description of the primitive Christian community of Jerusalem, which was considered programmatic for many of the eremitical and mendicant renewal movements of the twelfth and thirteenth centuries.¹⁴ The historical journey of the Order, like the spiritual journey of Elijah, can thus also be read as a model of transformation: the Carmelite, like his Order, is called to live a life centred on the Word of God in the ecclesial community animated by his Spirit and sharing in its mission.

3 Some Elijan themes in Books 2–6

Because the 'historical part' of the *Institutio* has been comparatively little read, some important elements of the image of Elijah held by medieval Carmelites have tended to be overlooked. Here I mention just some themes which seem of special significance.

3.1 Elijah, centre of a community of disciples

Elijah is generally seen as a solitary figure, a man of the desert who appears suddenly from out of the wilderness and just as suddenly returns to it again.¹⁵ For the most part this is the biblical picture of Elijah, who appears in the Books of Kings to have at most only a distant relationship with the circles of the sons of the prophets. His contact with these groups is mediated mainly through his disciple Elisha, whose relationship to these groups appears to be much clearer and more direct (2 K 2:1–7).¹⁶ As recent documents of the Order have pointed out, Elijah can rightly be seen as a man of the people, impelled by the living God to give effective witness to his presence in a world of injustice and religious crisis.¹⁷ These documents have come to stress the way in which the prophetic vocation of Elijah was realised through his solidarity with the poor and oppressed, so that he can be seen as an inspiration for new forms of spirituality, ministry and ecclesial presence; however, there is little to suggest that he might also be seen as a model of fraternal life. Our renewed reading of Elijah, based almost entirely on the biblical data alone, has not taken into account the way the same data were read (and sometimes misread) in the medieval context. This has created some difficulties, for the biblical data do not in fact

¹⁴ See for example M.-D. Chenu, *Nature, Man and Society in the Twelfth Century: Essays on New Theological Perspectives in the Latin West*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1968, esp. 202–269.

¹⁵ For some cautionary remarks about the desert theme and Elijah see Alexander Vella, 'Elijah's Wilderness Journey and the Desert Ideal', *Carmelus* 37 (1990); 3–37.

¹⁶ But see Kees Waaijman, *De profet Elia*, Nijmegen: Gottmer, 1985, 12–14.

¹⁷ *Constitutions* 1971, art. 14; General Congregation 1974, *The Carmelite Today*, 6; 1979 Council of Provinces, *Return to the Sources*; 1980 General Congregation, *Called to Account by the Poor*; etc.

seem to give us an image of Elijah which corresponds to some of the central values of the Order. This is particularly clear in the case of fraternity: why would a solitary remain the exemplar of an order of friars (*fratres*)?

In fact, the medieval Carmelites' reading of scripture stressed very strongly that Elijah is a man of fraternity and the founder and centre of a growing community of disciples.¹⁸ In this the Carmelites were men of their time: by the thirteenth century Elijah was increasingly being seen not so much as a completely solitary figure and model of eremitical life, as Peter Damian, for example had done,¹⁹ but rather as the model of solitude lived in community. The main emphasis of the Carmelite tradition as it is represented in the *Institutio* is on Elijah as a member of a community of disciples, drawn to live according to his example in the religious life which God has instituted through him.

Elijah's disciples are introduced in 2.2 (when they flee to Carith) and are a constant presence thereafter. They are *discipuli* and *imitatores*: in Elijah they see the pattern (*forma*) of the monastic way of life revealed to him by God. He is for them the *exemplar vivendi monastice* (2.8). He teaches them to prophesy, that is to sing praise to God with musical instruments (2.2). After his return from Horeb he assembles them on Mount Carmel, where he leads them in the observance of the monastic life and teaches them the *disciplina prophetica* (praise in song). As the number of communities grows he provides leaders for them (2.3). His principal disciples are treated at some length: Jonah, Elisha, Micaiah and Obadiah. Indeed all the forms of religious life are derived from Elijah 'as from the first and principal source' (2.8).

The *Institutio*'s interpretation of the theophany on Horeb is surprising and significant. In general medieval commentators, following Gregory the Great and others, saw Elijah's Horeb experience of the gentle breeze as a paradigm of contemplation and intimacy with God. The *Institutio* (3.2) takes the various elements of the theophany as prefigurations of those who will carry out the divine will (Hazael, Jehu, Elisha). The gentle breeze represents Elijah himself, whose task is to gather his disciples and other servants of God to peace and freedom after the time of repression: this mission is seen to be fulfilled in his construction of a community of peace, faith and true worship on Mount Carmel (3.3). Elijah spends eighteen years on Carmel in the company of his disciples, making the mountain a holy place forever (3.3). He is pre-eminently a man of love: the journey recorded in 2 K 2:1–9 is interpreted as a touching farewell to the various communities of the sons of the prophets; Elijah is concerned for their future without him and wishes to provide suitable leaders for them (4.3); he often leaves the solitude of contemplation to preach the word of God *propter utilitatem populi sui* (a phrase loaded with meaning for the medieval apostolic orders). The fiery and violent biblical Elijah is not absent from the *Institutio*, but it emphasises the peaceful aspects of his personality and mission: he brings peace to his disciples (3.2), and in the last days will return to intercede for humankind and to reconcile father and son (4.2).

¹⁸ In this there is a certain inconsistency in the *Institutio*: in book 1 Elijah is alone in Carith, but 2.2 asserts that during the persecutions of Jezebel devout men (the hundred prophets saved by Obadiah) fled to join him there and became the first of his disciples.

¹⁹ *Opusc.* 15.2; PL 103.145, 337.

3.2 Prophecy and liturgical prayer

The *Institutio* gives on several occasions a definition of prophecy: to prophesy (*prophetare*) means to sing psalms and hymns in praise of God with musical instruments. This is also called the *disciplina prophetica*. The definition is established with great care, and this kind of prophecy distinguished from prophecy in the sense of foretelling the future, the latter being a gift which only God can give, even though the two are sometimes associated (2.3). The biblical background, of course, is the ecstatic prophecy of 1 Sam 5:10–12; 19:20–24, etc., but the point made is about the importance of liturgical prayer, which is given a large place in Carmelite life as depicted in the *Institutio*. It is a feature of daily life on Carmel: three times a day the sons of the prophets leave their caves and cells to gather in the *semnion*, where they join as one in praise of the Creator and in openness to the Word of God (3.3). The effect of the jubilant singing of the psalms is to open the heart to God's Spirit (cf. 2 K 3:11–19; 2:3).

This association of prophecy and praise needs further research to situate it in its background in medieval religious thought. It was current in the thirteenth century as one can see from the biblical commentaries, but as far as I know there has been no study of it. Jacopone da Todi seems to refer to this idea in one of his *Laude*, where he links it to love: 'How can this overflowing love be suppressed? / The jubilation will out / as Elias once learned / in prophetic song'.²⁰ The same tradition was mentioned in the charter founding our house in Lisbon in 1424, where the Carmelites promise to use musical instruments on solemn feasts because they were used by Elijah and Elisha on Carmel. The tradition entered the Constitutions and remained there, surprisingly, until 1968, but it now seems to have been forgotten.

The definition of prophecy as praise—though it may seem at first sight an unpromising idea—could prove a rich theme. It links prophecy with contemplation and with the prayer of the community; it emphasises that listening-in-solitude and the coming out of solitude into the gathering of the community are inseparable aspects of openness to the Word of God; and it gives great stress to the relationship between prophecy, public worship and the (re)construction of community which is already part of the biblical story of Elijah.

3.3 The spiritual knowledge of scripture: *lectio divina*

The centre of the prophet's life, of course, is the Word of God. Elijah is above all a person open to the Word, his life is lived in obedience to it, his service to Israel is communication of God's Word. The community on Mount Carmel gathers three times daily to hear the Word in the Law and the Prophets (3.3). When Elijah returns in the last days, he will have the task of reconciling fathers and sons. This is interpreted, following St Augustine, as teaching the Jews the true meaning of the scriptures, that they may understand them as did their fathers the prophets (4.2).

The search for the true meaning of the Word has an important place in Book 5, which deals with the conversion of the sons of the prophets to Christianity. As sons of the prophets and faithful Israelites they had always longed for the Messiah. May had received the baptism of John, and so had been prepared to recognise the Messiah when he came;

²⁰ Lauda 25 [80], in *Jacopone da Todi: The Lauds*, trans. S. and E. Hughes, (Classics of Western Spirituality 30), New York: Paulist Press, 1982, 233–234.

some in fact were John's assistants and so were present when Jesus was baptised. In Jerusalem they heard the preaching of the apostles at Pentecost and so were converted. (The *Institutio* says ingeniously that scripture proves that the Carmelites were there to hear Saint Peter preach, for he names them explicitly when he says 'You are the sons of the prophets'! [Acts 3:25].) However, not all of them had understood the prophecy of John and some held back from conversion until, through prayer in the temple and witnessing the miracle worked there by Peter, their doubts were removed (5.6-5.7). Whether one is charmed or affronted by the naïveté of these fictions is a matter of taste, but important spiritual values are being expressed: attentiveness to the Word drawing the believer to Christ and creating a longing for the fulfilment of God's promises; openness to the movements of the Spirit; the popular, 'ecclesial' and liturgical context of hearing the Word (the crowds who flocked to John, the celebration of the Pasch in Jerusalem, the prayer in the Temple); the spiritual diversity of the community and its need for a process of communal discernment based on prayerful attentiveness to the Word.

A very important text on this theme is Book 5 Chapter 8, which concludes the 'history' of the sons of the prophets. As the *Institutio* began with a scriptural text (1 K 17:2-4), so it ends with one: 'They remained faithful to the teaching of the apostles, to the brotherhood, to the breaking of bread. Every day they went together to the temple, praising God with gladness and simplicity of heart' (Acts 2:42, 46). The order instituted by God's command to Elijah now continues in faithfulness to the full revelation made in the Incarnate Word. Its image now is the apostolic community, addressed in a completely new way by the Word and responsible for preaching it to the world.

After their conversion, Book 5 continues, the Carmelites persevere in meditating, as they had always done, on the sacred books, but now they are able to read them in their spiritual or allegorical meaning: 'Every old law seemed to them like an animal, insofar as it has the literal meaning as its outside, like a body, but on the inside, inside the letter, there lay hidden like a soul the invisible and spiritual sense of a profound and divine mystery.' The nourishment they drew from this source led them to preach Christ in Phoenicia and Palestine (5.8).

3.4 Mount Carmel, place of peace and fraternal harmony

Carmel was irrevocably associated with Elijah in the medieval mind, not only because of the biblical events which took place there (Elijah's contest with the prophets of Baal, his prayer for rain, etc.), but because it was believed that Elijah spent the remainder of his life there as a hermit (eighteen years is the traditional timespan). His presence drew there the community of disciples with which the Carmelites considered themselves in spiritual and historical continuity. For the *Institutio* this place, where Elijah had shown that the God of Israel is the living and true God, is the perfect place for the practice of the eremitical religious life. From it the order drew its name, and in other places where they settled the Carmelites continued to be named after it because wherever they were they practised the same life that Elijah and his followers lived on Carmel (3.5). Carmel is the utopia of the Carmelites.

What is most striking about the descriptions of life on Carmel is the emphasis on peace and harmony in fraternal life. The construction of true community is based on the same spiritual dynamic seen in Book 1: purity of heart leads from sin to love and to the works of charity; silence (which, as we have seen in Book 1, is a form of receptivity)

brings quarrels and strife to an end and bears fruit in unity of heart and true justice. In the beauty of peace the disciples are enabled to taste contemplatively the delights of God's love and to celebrate it in common worship (3.5). (It is worth noting in passing the centrality of harmony and peace in community in the *Fiery Arrow*, where Nicholas' opposition to active ministry by those not spiritually prepared for it is largely based on its destructive effects on community life—a theme that deserves further exploration in early Carmelite literature). Carmel in the *Institutio* reflects the values of Elijah himself: uncompromising faith in the God of Israel, openness to the Word, and practice of the justice of the covenant brings inner reconciliation with God and his people, and so leads to blessing and peace, both inner and outer.

So profound is the peace created and given on Carmel that it becomes an island of peace even in time of war and the Carmelites are preserved by God from deportation and captivity: 'They were so peacefully disposed to one another that there was no conflict among them. In their speech they were armed with silence, for there was no talkativeness among them, and so they were quiet of heart and secure, because their hearts did not accuse them before God. Therefore, confident that God protected them, whom they always strove to please, they had no fear of their enemies. As the Wise Man says: "When the ways of a man are pleasing to God, he will convert even his enemies to peace"' (4.7).

3.5 Elijah and Mary, Christocentricity and messianic longing

While some Carmelite writings of the fourteenth century had emphasised the Elijan character and foundation of the order (Baconthorpe's *Compendium*, Cheminetto's *Speculum*), others had emphasised its Marian title and devotion (Baconthorpe's *Speculum* and treatise on the Rule),²¹ without being entirely successful in integrating these two approaches. Book 6 of the *Institutio* links Elijah and Mary in the prophet's vision of the little cloud, which is interpreted as a revelation of the future coming of the Messiah, born of a virgin. This interpretation, though complex in some ways, is satisfying and coherent on a number of levels, uniting the exemplarity of Elijah and Mary not only on a symbolic and mythical level but also in the sphere of the fundamental values of Carmelite spirituality. The stress on Mary's virginity and freedom from sin, her total openness to God's word and purpose, and the Christocentricity of her life, tie in with the great spiritual themes of the work, especially with the purity of heart which allows the word and grace of God to bear fruit in an authentic life grounded in love. In the *Institutio* there is no unresolved tension in having both Elijah and Mary as inspiration for the Carmelite vocation.

In this context, however, I simply wish to emphasise one aspect of the *Institutio*'s little cloud story relevant to the Elijan themes of the work. The biblical Elijah is not a messianic prophet, but the *Institutio* provides him with a vision of the coming of the Virgin Mother and the Saviour. The mysteries revealed to him in the vision of the little cloud Elijah passes on to his disciples (6.4): thenceforth they never cease to pray for the incarnation of the Son of God. Part of the inheritance they receive from Elijah is messianic longing, and their characteristic prayer is one directed to the realisation of God's promises in the coming of the Saviour. Their devotion to Mary is therefore presented as a natural

²¹ These texts have been edited by Adrianus Staring, *Medieval Carmelite Heritage: Early Reflections on the Nature of the Order*, (Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, 16), Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1989.

development of their relationship with the prophet, and the Christocentricity of Carmelite spirituality also becomes, paradoxically, an 'Elijan theme', just as in Book 1 the life of an Old Testament prophet is explained as an entirely evangelical life.

4. Conclusion

From the point of view of the history of spirituality, there is a great deal of work to be done on the Elijah-tradition of the Order. Even from a brief survey it is clear that some elements of the tradition have been virtually forgotten, and our knowledge of the larger medieval context in which the 'Carmelite Elijah' was constructed is very fragmentary. The order's most recent attempts to express the meaning of Elijah for Carmelite spirituality have all used the biblical texts as their principal or exclusive source, and this has made it difficult for us to remain in continuity with the meaning Elijah had in the charismatic experience of the first Carmelites and with the way his significance was developed by subsequent tradition. The real source of Carmelite ideas about Elijah is not so much scripture as such but the medieval reading of scripture.

The *Institutio* draws on this tradition to present a remarkably rich picture of Elijah, as prophet, contemplative, hearer of the Word, seeker of authenticity, servant of the people, man of fraternity, father of disciples, builder of peace, a man in wait for the fulfillment of God's promise of salvation, one transformed by his experience of the love of God. These themes are only partly understood and only partly represented in the order's contemporary consciousness of Elijah as an inspirational figure.